

Influence of Job Enrichment on Performance of Academic Staff in Public Universities in Kenya

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Abstract: The study herein aims to examine the impact of job enrichment on the performance of academic staff in public universities in Kenya. The study uses data collected from all academic staff in Kenyan public universities who form the target population. Further, the study employed exploratory research which enabled the researcher to achieve greater control of the study design, and the use of a cross-sectional survey since the data used was collected during the research and was not initially centrally available. Data collection was undertaken using questionnaires distributed to a select number of staff derived using the multi-stage sampling procedure. Using simple regression models for data analysis, the research established that there is a positive correlation between job enrichment and the performance of academic staff in public universities in Kenya. Based on the above findings, it is recommended that further research is required to analyze the impact of job enrichment on non-academic staff. Further, extensive research should be undertaken to establish similarities of findings in the case where the target population is private university staff.

Keywords: Job Enrichment, Exploratory Research, Multi-Stage Analysis, Academic Staff

I. Introduction

The performance of an institution is greatly impacted by various factors that tend to lean more on job satisfaction. Job satisfaction on the other hand is dependent on the nature and design of the job profiles available (Munyiri, 2018). An institution, whether large or small, must take into account the state of its employees' job satisfaction as this is a critical driver for success. Given the competitive nature of the prevailing global working environment, there is a need to monitor and motivate a firm's greatest asset, its human resource (Chan, Gee, & Steiner, 2000). The productivity of employees is directly proportional to the success rate of the institution within which they work. It is critical to note that while there is the staff who naturally have a self-motivation attribute, a greater percentage have been found by researchers to not possess the self-motivation trait that pushes them to consistently grow their effectiveness (Chan, Gee, & Steiner, 2000).

In light of the above assertion, the job design of an institution must be aligned with its capacity to motivate employees to enhance productivity (Mohr & Puck, 2007). The needs of each employee vary from one entity to another, and this gives rise to a series of variables that impact job performance (Muhammad, 2013). One such variable is the job enrichment factor. The research herein is thus challenged to establish whether or not job enrichment impacts the job performance of employees, with consideration of the staff in public universities in Kenya.

The main objective of the research is to establish the influence of job enrichment on the job performance of academic staff in public universities. There exist various related research works and theories that describe job enrichment concerning performance. The research herein considered the Herzberg Motivation-Hygiene Theory which states that unique job factors are linked to the satisfaction of staff, whereas there are factors that can also lead to job dissatisfaction (Herzberg, 2005). Herzberg labeled motivational factors as satisfiers and described them as innate attributes that staff possess and, which enable them to attain satisfaction at different levels as well as experiences on the job (Settles, 2006). Zareen and Razzaq (2013), the point is that job enrichment is perceived in three ways which include task

identity, significance, and autonomy. The researcher argues that with the above three attributes, the staff can perceive the same as growth in job enrichment and this tends towards better job performance.

II. Methods

2.1 Research Design

The study applied the exploratory research design whose sole purpose was to achieve greater control of the study (Bernhard & Sverke, 2003). Further, the research employed the cross-sectional survey which was arrived at because the data was gathered at that specific point in time.

2.2 Target Population

The target population for the study was all academic staff employed in all public universities in Kenya. The total populace of the staff is 8294 (UASU, 2018). The research assumed that the target population entailed every academic staff regardless of the level of education and seniority.

2.3 Sampling Frame

A sampling frame refers to the spread of the population from which the research picks a sample. The frame may be a list, but these are rare. Instead, researchers often have a compiled alternative list (Nachmias & Nachmias, 2007). The research herein applied the sample frame of staff in the 31 chartered public universities in Kenya (UASU, 2018).

2.4 Sampling Size and Sampling Technique

The research applied a multi-stage sampling technique. The specific technique applied was the two-stage sampling technique which dictates that the primary units must be present in the secondary sampling unit. In this case, the former is the staff in public universities and the latter is the public universities in Kenya.

3.4.1 Sample size determination

The sample size was determined using Nassiuma's (2000), formula.

(1)

$$n = \frac{NC^2}{C^2 + (N - 1)e^2}$$

Where

n = sample size

N = Population size

c = co-variance (21% ≤ c ≤ 30%)

e = standard error (2% ≤ e ≤ 5%)

$$n = \frac{31(0.21)^2}{0.21^2 + (31 - 1)0.05^2} = 11$$

It was prudent to select a university for which pre-testing was carried out on the premise of Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), who posited that a single participant is used for pre-testing but is excluded from the sample used. The determination of staff in ten institutions was derived using the very formula by Naissuma (2000).

$$n = \frac{2491(0.30)^2}{0.30^2 + (2491 - 1)0.02^2} = 206$$

2.4.2 Sampling Techniques

Multi-stage sampling entailed a random selection of 10 universities from the 31 chartered public universities in Kenya. The essence was to apply a simple random sampling based on the lottery technique. Such a technique allows equal probability for respondents to be selected. The second phase of the technique entailed the selection of the staff for the research from the sampled 10. The sampling used was the random sampling technique.

2.5 Data Collection Instruments

The research applied primary data which was collected via a questionnaire. The questionnaires were distributed to academic staff selected randomly. The selection of questionnaires is preferred as it enables the researcher to acquire more feedback with regards to the large size of respondents within a limited time. It was therefore the most convenient and effective data collection tool (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). The questionnaire was built on a 5-Point Likert scale that measured the variables from 1-strongly agree, 2-disagree, 3-neutral neither agree nor disagree, 4-agree, 5-strongly agree to measure the variables under study.

2.6 Data Collection Procedure

The questionnaire administration was on a drop and pick basis with the aid of research assistants. The researcher observed ethical research considerations by seeking permission from appropriate authorities before contacting and sharing the questionnaires. There was the visitation of the area of study for purposes of familiarisation to enable ease of operation during the final research undertaking. The authorities in charge of the university staff in question offered permission and guidance on a material day on data collection and the rules and regulations to observe.

2.7 Data Processing and Analysis

The data collected via the questionnaires was qualitative because it sought to establish the status of various variables (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2013). Data analysis is the review of data to enable obtain meaningful information (Saunders, Lewis & Thornbill, 2009). On the other hand, data processing entails the interpretation of data to be able to use it statistically and deduce meaning (Hyndman et al., 2008). The data analysis for the research was undertaken using SPSS Version 20.

Multiple linear regression was applied to enable the evaluation of the influence of job enrichment on the performance of academic staff in public universities in Kenya. Given that the overall job design was applied as a variable, the Multiple Linear Regression Model employed measured various other job design variables as illustrated in the model below.

(2)

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

Where: Y = composite score performance of academic staff ; X_1 = composite score for job enrichment; X_2 = composite score job enlargement; X_3 = composite score job multi skilling; X_4 = composite work flexibility.

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ and β_4 are the regression coefficients indicating the influence of each of the independent variables ($X_i, i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) to Y .

β_0 Represents the constant (intercept)

ε Represents error term which is usually distributed with a mean zero and constant variance of σ^2 .

(3)

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 M + \beta_6 (X_1 * M) + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

Where:

Y = composite score performance of academic staff

X_1 = composite score for job enrichment

X_2 = composite score job enlargement

X_3 = composite score job multi skilling

X_4 = composite work flexibility

M = moderating variable (say gender)

$X_1 * M X_1 * M$ Represents an interaction term between moderating variable (Gender) and job Enrichment.

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ and, are the regression coefficients showing the contribution of each of the independent variables ($X_i, i = 1, 2, 3, 4$). β_5 and β_6 are regression coefficients indicating the contribution of the main effect of the moderating variable and the interaction term to Y respectively.

β_0 Represents the constant (intercept)

E Represent error term which is usually distributed with a mean zero and constant.

Variance of σ^2 .

III. Results

3.1 Introduction

The section indicates the results of the research. The raw data obtained were coded and analyzed to give the results herein. The section herein is coordinated as follows, initial a conversation of the reaction rate, assessment of exploration instruments, and afterward the aftereffects of clear insights of the segment qualities of respondents in the investigation. These are trailed by acquiring the variables of the examination by changing the coded crude information (total measures). This at that point considered getting the descriptive statistics of the investigation factors and the related examination. In the following segment, the regression was done and followed by the trial of the hypothesis. Finally, the section introduced a discussion of the results of the examination. Data analysis was grounded on the goals of the investigation where the overall target of the examination was to discover the impact of job enrichment on the performance of academic staff in public universities in Kenya. job enrichment, alongside enlargement, and multi-skilling and work flexibility from the independent variables that impact job designs overall. The control variables in the investigation were the individual attributes, which notwithstanding, Gender, Experience, Designation, and Terms of Service. Control variables were analyzed to establish the impact of each variable with regards to how job enrichment affects the performance of academic staff in public universities in Kenya.

3.1.1 Response Rate

The unit of analysis in this exploration was the scholastic staff as every scholarly staff's duty execution is impacted contrastingly by job enrichment amongst other factors. Questionnaires were disseminated to 206 academic staff in 10 state-funded universities in Kenya. Out of the normal 206 surveys, just 170 polls were finished and returned in a structure usable for investigation. The reaction rate for this examination was 82.5%. This reaction rate shows a satisfactory image of the sample and the entire populace and is viewed as sufficient as upheld by Mugenda and Mugenda, (2003).

Missing value analysis was performed and 7 reactions were found to have missing values bigger than 5%. Complete case deletion was utilized, and the 7 reactions were ignored and discarded from further review. The excess lacking information was presumed to be missing entirely leaving 163 cases for examination. A review of the missing information designs in this way showed that the quantities of missing estimations of the investigation factors were little and arbitrarily conveyed.

3.1.2 Reliability and Validity

The investigation needed to ensure that the exploration tools estimated (the information assortment instruments) what they were expected to estimate. As such, those tools were reliable and valid. The resulting subsection talks about the results of the tests for validity and dependability.

3.1.2.1 Test of Reliability

The exploration questionnaire was examined to decide its unwavering quality. To test the internal constancy of the scale items, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was utilized. The results of the investigation are depicted in Table 1.

Table 1

Variable	No of Items	Alpha (α)
Job Enrichment	11	0.829
Job Enlargement	9	0.859
Multi skilling	6	0.820
Work Flexibility	9	0.791
Academic Staff Performance	12	0.831

As established in TABLE, totally the examination constructs had alpha coefficients of 0.7 or more. This shows that the instrument met the limit of 0.7 as proposed by Nunnally and Bernstein (1994) and henceforth thought to be reliable. This at that point infers that the constructs in the survey are consistent.

3.1.2.2 Test of Validity

Factor analysis was undertaken to test and find out the validity of the research. Because of the huge number of respondents included, separate arrangements of factor analysis were accomplished for the items in the research constructs. Factor analysis was utilized to check the degree to which every item in the scales added to the individual factor. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) for things in job enrichment was undertaken. In undertaking the EFA, the two most generally utilized extraction techniques are principal axis factoring or head pivot figuring. The two methodologies create comparative outcomes in most research circumstances (Gaur and Gaur 2011; Hair et al., 2011). This examination utilized principal component analysis and varimax pivot due to their wide utilization and straightforwardness.

To validate the utilization of factor analysis, the Kaiser Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy (MSA) is regularly utilized. Kaiser Meyer-Olkin's measure differs from 0 to 1.0 and values close to 1 are better. An estimation of 0.5 is encouraged least to continue with factor analysis (Hair et al., 2011). One more methodology of finding the fittingness of factor analysis is by leading Bartlett's test of sphericity, a statistical test for the presence of relationships among the factors. A numerically critical Bartlett's test of sphericity shows that enough connections exist among the factors to progress with factor analysis (Hair et al., 2011). In this research, the Kaiser MeyerOlkin measure and Bartlett's test of sphericity were utilized.

3.2 Job enrichment

The research aimed to portray the job enrichment of the scholarly staff in public universities. Respondents were approached to determine how much they concurred that the proclamations on the things of measurements of job enrichment portrayed their performance. The components of job enrichment were task importance, identity, and independence/autonomy. Every item had a 5-point Likert-type scale, going from 'strongly disagree' (1) to 'strongly agree' (5). The answers accorded were assessed using mean scores, standard deviations, and coefficient of variations. The higher mean scores showed solid concession to the variables construct and the lower mean score showed solid disparity with the assertions of the variable construct.

Table 2 describes findings of job enrichment on the performance of academic staff.

Table 2				
Item	N	Mean	SD	CV (%)
Task Identity		3.98		
1. My work involves completing a piece of work that has an obvious beginning and end.	163	3.97	0.990	24.95%
2. My work is arranged so that I can do an entire piece of work from beginning to end.	163	3.98	0.910	22.87%
3. My work gives me the chance to finish the pieces of work I began.	163	3.99	0.871	21.82%
Task Significance		4.36		
1. The results of my job are likely to pointedly affect the lives of other people within and outside the university	163	4.36	0.737	16.89%
2. My work is very significant and important in the broader objective of the university	163	4.35	0.767	17.64%
Task Autonomy		3.86		
1. My work allows me to make my own decisions about how to schedule my tasks.	163	3.83	0.975	25.48%
2. My work allows me to decide on the order in which things are done on the job.	163	3.81	0.912	23.93%
3. My work gives me a chance to use my initiative and judgment in doing the work	163	4.10	0.739	18.03%
4. My work allows me to make a lot of decisions on my own.	163	3.75	1.040	27.71%
5. My current job offers me significant autonomy in making decisions	163	3.75	0.902	24.03%
6. My work gives me the considerable opportunity for independence and freedom in how I should do it.	163	3.91	0.873	22.31%
Overall Mean		4.07		

The results as shown in the Table illustrate that the mean score for the constructs of the identity dimension of the job enrichment variables is 3.98. The construct with the greatest score was 'My work provides me the chance to finish the pieces of work I began.' (M =3.99., SD =0.871); the construct with the least score was 'My work involves finishing a piece of work that has an obvious start and end.' (M = 3.97, SD = 0.990). Among the factored items of task identity, the item factor with the highest variability was 'My work involves completing a piece of work that has an obvious beginning and end.' (CV = 24.95%) and the variable with the lowest variability was 'My work provides me the opportunity to finish the pieces of work I began.' (CV = 21.82%). The general task importance had the top mean of 4.34. The same is seconded by task identity with a mean of 3.96 and task autonomy with a mean score of 3.84. The aforementioned findings portray that the respondents greatly agreed that the availed statements sufficed their intuitions.

IV. Discussion

The primary target of the research was to analyze the impact of job enrichment on the execution of duties by scholarly staff in state-funded universities in Kenya. As per the finding, the majority of the academic staff concurred that the work they perform furnished them with the opportunity to completely complete the bits of work they started. Among the three things in work advancement, task importance had the most elevated mean score, next was task personality and task independence. This meant that the respondents firmly concurred with the assertions concerning task importance in their institutions. The results uncovered that in the work enrichment practice, the

assurance of assignment importance, task personality, and self-sufficiency would improve the work done by the scholarly staff.

Correlation analysis and simple regression analysis were applied in the examination to analyze the connection between job enrichment and the output of academic staff in public universities in Kenya. The analysis of the correlation results showed a critical positive direct connection between job improvement and execution of duties by public university scholastic staff. Simple Regression analysis showed that Work improvement all alone (regardless of different parts of job design which were work extension, multiskilling, and work adaptability) was a genuinely huge indicator of the performance of scholarly staff in state-funded universities in Kenya. The discoveries uphold that work enhancement is a significant factor to consider in improving the work estimation of scholarly staff. The positive connection bolsters the advantages of changing the present place of employment plan in state-funded colleges in Kenya. The finding agrees with those of Vijay and Tamilnadu (2015) whose review displayed a positive and a critical connection between job enrichment and Individual Execution among Resources with Unique Reference to a Private College. The outcomes likewise concur with the discoveries of Ahmed (2018), whose exploration work additionally agreed that work advancement had a positive huge impact on the execution of representatives of the International Centre for research and agro-forestry. Because of the positive relationship between job improvement and the improvement of organizations' execution of duties, it is clear that the scholastic staff at state-funded colleges in Kenya need job enrichment procedures to improve the result of their work.

In any case, after additional examination utilizing the various regression models, the outcomes showed an immaterial negative direct relationship between work enhancement and execution of duties by scholarly staff while holding Job enlargement, Multi skilling, and Work flexibility constant. The outcomes can be perceived and clarified differently. One of the clarifications of the outcome above is credited to a clarification given by research done on the relationship between the factors above. Vijay et al (2015) just split the variable job enrichment into three subcomponents, which is comparable to doing the basic regression on job enrichment.

V. Conclusion

The research herein sought to examine the impact of job enrichment on the performance of academic staff in public universities in Kenya. The research established that there is a positive correlation between job enrichment and the performance of academic staff in public universities in Kenya. The research merits in various aspects as its findings are critical in policy-making for not only university academic staff, but civil servants as well as private employers, concerning the formulation of effective policies relating to the productivity of staff. Despite the aforementioned merit, the paper is limited in its scope. Given that there are public and private universities and academic and non-academic staff, the paper is limited as it fails to review the perspectives of the aforementioned respondents.

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